

THE HELPFUL WEBSITE FOR TEACHING ENGLISH TO KIDS

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Abstract

This article gives information about the helpful website (learnenglishkids) for teaching english to kids. It describes what kinds of materials are available in the website. And it also shows how useful they are for using second language teaching process.

Key words: kids, website, poems, songs, videos, short stories.

Introduction

teaching foreign languages to kids is more difficult than adults and teenagers. Because they are a bit lazy to learn new words in foreign language and they can not manage to comprehend rules of grammar, to express their ideas in second language writing and speaking. That's why, some scholars have carried out many researches on how to teach english to kids efficiently. However, other linguists have found a new way of teaching them effectively by establishing various websites like <http://learnenglishkids.britishcouncil.org> in order to use them in teaching process. Because they believe that it will be easier to teach english effectively with the help of these kinds of websites. "the complexity to learn english tends on requiring the need to resort to websites as technological tools to improve the skills of this foreign language" (macancela., j.m. 2019).

"learnenglish kids is designed for children up to 12 years old to use on their own, with parents and friends or in class" (budden., jo). This website is really helpful for teachers to employ during teaching process. Because there exist so many instructional videos, authentic materials and games based on them. In the following paragraphs, detailed information about them is given.

Materials:

- poems

There are a mixed variety of intriguing poems which can help kids to take pleasure from english learning process. These are very easy to understand for kids. That's why, they can learn them by heart easily. "by inviting students to be "in the poem" actively reading poems in pairs or other small groupings, and creating ideas together, poetry can become an integral part of the efl classroom and can be a means of investigating issues relevant to the students' backgrounds, experiences, and attitude" (finch, andrew. 2003).

- songs

Different types of websites are available in the website which can help teachers to encourage their students to be energetic with these songs' amazing actions which are showed in the given videos.

- short stories

In this website, short stories are also given to improve kid's listening comprehension and critical thinking about what they receive from the given story passage. These are really helpful and enjoyable for kids who are very eager to learn english language as a second language.

- videos

watching videos is a great way of learning english and new things about different intriguing topics. This has a mixed variety of not only motivational videos but also entertaining ones. There are given activities based on the videos to identify how well students comprehend the video in english language.

Conclusion

second language teaching is a bit difficult process for esl teachers who teach little kids at early age. Because they are a bit naughty and they are likely to be bored sooner than older learners. That's why, teachers should learn various kinds of digital tools like websites in order to prevent kids from being in a boring second language learning process. The most useful website for using in teaching english to kids is learnenglishkids. This website has a lot of authentic materials which can make little learners indulgent in intriguing foreign language learning atmosphere.

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